

"One Unorganized Youth for Every Graduate" Program as a Tool for Enhancing the Activities of Future Physical Education and Sports Specialists

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Annotation:

This article highlights the content of the program "One unorganized youth for every graduate" aimed at a new level of involvement of unorganized youth in physical education and mass sports in mahallas, as well as at developing the professional competence of future athletes and sports specialists.

Keywords: unorganized youth, physical education, sports, neighborhood, independent activities of students to the association.

Revising the content of personnel training for the socio-economic development of new Uzbekistan and creating necessary conditions for preparing highly qualified specialists to international standards In accordance with the priority tasks for the socio-economic development of New Uzbekistan, the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan and the government have adopted and are implementing several decrees and resolutions aimed at fundamentally revising the content of personnel training and creating the necessary conditions for preparing highly qualified specialists to meet international standards. Among these initiatives are: The Decree[1], PF-5447 of August 8, 2019, "On the Approval of the Concept for the Development of the Higher Education System of the Republic of Uzbekistan until 2030" which outlines the long-term strategy for higher education development. The Decree[2], PF-5924 of January 24, 2020, by the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan, "On Measures to Further Improve and Promote Physical Education and Sports in the Republic of Uzbekistan," which aims to enhance and popularize physical education and sports. The Decree[3], PF-209 of December 21, 2023, which focuses on increasing the role of mahalla (local community) institutions in society and ensuring their function as a primary link in solving public

issues. The Decree, PF-6108 of November 6,2020, "On Measures for the Development of Education, Training, and Science in the New Development Era of Uzbekistan," which emphasizes the systematic organization of professional practice for each student in relevant industries and organizations from the second year of their studies, and the need for specific measures to organize practical training directly in production and facilitate graduate employment. These documents collectively stress the importance of integrating practical experience into academic programs and ensuring that graduates are well-prepared for the workforce. They highlight the necessity of systematic professional practice and direct organizational measures to support student internships and employment opportunities [4].

Focusing on the Development of Young People in the Context of Building New Uzbekistan and Improving the Mahalla System

In our country, achieving the grand goal of establishing New Uzbekistan and making rapid strides on the path of a third renaissance relies significantly on giving special attention and care to our diligent youth. It is essential to create the necessary conditions and opportunities for them to fully demonstrate their talents and potential across all fields. Enhancing the mahalla (local community) system is considered a priority in state policy.

As President Sh. Mirziyoyev has emphasized, "The times are changing rapidly. It is necessary to transform the mahalla into an institution that truly addresses local issues. We will gain more experience and make further changes. Life compels us to do so. If we seek solutions to current challenges, our only path is mahalla, mahalla, mahalla, and once again mahalla. The more we raise the prestige of the mahalla system, the more people will trust us and be satisfied with us"[5]. This is not just an empty assertion but a critical directive for our efforts.

Based on these legal foundations, our scientific research aims to address the outlined tasks by applying the "One Unorganized Youth for Every Graduate" program in our country. This program is designed to engage future physical education and sports specialists, currently studying in higher education institutions, with mahalla and sector-specific areas, thereby fulfilling the objectives mentioned above.

Objectives of the "One Unorganized Youth for Every Graduate" Program:

To ensure the implementation of decisions and decrees issued by the President and government of the Republic of Uzbekistan regarding physical education and mass sports[6];

- To strengthen collaboration between higher education institutions and mahallas (local communities) or sectoral areas in organizing activities related to physical education and mass sports.
- To provide close support to the activities of youth leaders in mahallas.
- To prepare mahalla teams for sports events under the "Five Initiatives Olympics."
- To assist students in finding their place in society according to their future specialties.
- To promote and increase the popularity of physical education and mass sports activities.
- To widely advocate for a healthy lifestyle among the population and youth.
- To assist in preventing criminal activities and offenses among youth and unorganized groups.
- To conduct "Physical Fitness Level" sports tests among the population.
- To develop the professional competence of future physical education and sports specialists.

- To work specifically with youth classified in red and yellow categories in mahallas, following a detailed plan.

Requirements for Future Specialists:

- To collaborate with the mahalla (local community) leadership.
- To continuously develop their physical and academic potential.
- To adhere to universal ethical and moral standards.
- To seek guidance from mahalla elders in their work.
- To possess skills in modern information communication technologies and internet usage.
- To have self-confidence and a clear sense of purpose.
- To value the profession of physical education and sports specialist.
- To be capable of regularly assessing physical development indicators based on age categories of the population.

Procedure for Future Specialists to Participate in the Program:

- Submit an application.
- Undergo an interview.
- Enter into a contract with the mahalla organization.
- Develop a program and plans for annual activities.
- Provide quarterly reports on their activities.
- Participate in events organized by the mahalla, sports administration, and youth affairs agency.

Responsibilities of Higher Education Institutions:

- Provide preparatory courses for future physical education and sports specialists to participate in the program. These courses will include information on the program's objectives and tasks, as well as methodologies for organizing activities.
- Monitor students' activities.
- Offer methodological support to students.
- Assist in promoting students' activities through mass media.
- Evaluate students' performance.
- Encourage students who actively participate throughout the year.
- Provide employers with opportunities to identify talented students.

Responsibilities of the Mahalla within the Program:

- Provide all necessary conditions for students participating in the "One Unorganized Youth for Every Graduate" program (such as a dedicated room, computer equipment, and sports gear).
- Offer regular incentives to students participating in the program every quarter.

Responsibilities of Students within the Program:

- Familiarize themselves with the mahalla's infrastructure.
- Collaborate with the mahalla leadership in a cooperative manner.

- Execute the tasks specified in the annual plans and programs on time.
- Prepare reports on completed activities.
- Make regular appearances in mass media.

To become a participant in the "One Unorganized Youth for Every Graduate" program, students must include in their application form information about their background, familiarity with the program's content, objectives, and tasks, their opinions and suggestions about the program, as well as the expected outcomes from their participation.

Within the Program, Students Are Expected to:

- Acquire general information about the youth in the mahalla.
- Prepare athletes for the "Five Initiatives Olympics."
- Promote a healthy lifestyle among the population.
- Prepare and conduct "Physical Fitness Level" sports tests and competitions for the community.
- Organize events aimed at preventing criminal activities and offenses among youth.
- Motivate unorganized youth to engage in mass sports.
- Assist in fostering patriotism among youth.
- Work individually with aggressive and unorganized youth.

Expected Outcomes for Future Specialists through the Program:

- Development of creativity skills such as adaptability, teamwork, and the ability to express their ideas freely.
- Enhancement of self-assessment skills.
- Development of a sense of responsibility toward the profession.
- Advancement of professional competencies through the continuous application of theoretical knowledge in practice.
- Further improvement of professional capabilities.

Expected Outcomes for Higher Education Institutions through the Program:

- Achieving a continuous integration of practical experience into the educational process.
- Refinement of students' professional practical skills.
- Effective execution of independent learning tasks.
- Creation of a creative environment for career orientation.
- Expansion of opportunities for students to conduct scientific experiments.

Expected Outcomes for the Mahalla through the Program:

- Formation of a healthy lifestyle across all age groups in the community.
- Opportunity to discover talented individuals among unorganized youth.
- Improvement in the quality of the "Five Initiatives Olympics" competitions.
- Increased public engagement in physical education and mass sports through extensive promotion in mahallas and sectors.
- Systematic administration of "Physical Fitness Level" sports tests.

- Enhanced opportunities for preventing criminal activities and offenses among youth, particularly unorganized groups.
- Reduction in the number of youth classified in the red category.

In conclusion, In today's context, it is crucial to address numerous issues impacting the quality of professional training for competitive, highly qualified specialists in physical education and mass sports. Implementing a methodological system to enhance the professional competence of future specialists in physical education and sports will contribute to the development of motivational foundations for graduates in their chosen professions. It will also aid in their social self-awareness, foster professional optimism, build self-confidence, and improve emotional and psychological traits, all of which are critical for their professional competence development.

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